

Basilica of Saint Demetrios

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The cross-transept basilica dedicated to saint Demetrios the Myroblyte (the myrrh-gusher), located in the centre of the city of Thessaloniki (Northern Greece), was considered a major pilgrimage. It is believed that it was built by the Roman governor named Leontios in the third quarter of the 5th century CE, following the transfer of the cult of Saint Demetrios from Sirmium (present day city of Sremska Mitrovica, Serbia) to Thessaloniki. The first church on the site was constructed in the early 4th century on a complex of Roman buildings, including a bath that was incorporated in the crypt, under the sanctuary. This was the place where, according to tradition, the saint was imprisoned and martyred. The crypt became since the early Christian period the main place of worship of the martyr, and was related to the belief that myrrh flowed from his wounds. Pilgrims were therefore entering the small semi circular room with the ciborium in the middle, for receiving the miraculous myrrh. The 5th-century church was burnt between 629 and 634 but was restored immediately thereafter, under the care of the bishop of Thessaloniki and Leo the eparch, as mentioned by the mosaic inscription that accompanies the depiction of the saint and the two individuals. The 7th-century church retained the precedent form of the basilica, reincorporating large parts of it as well. Fire destroyed again the monument in 1917, which was rebuilt with original materials and fragments. The basilica has five aisles separated by four rows of columns with two pairs of large piers interposed amongst the columns of the central aisle. The church also includes a three-aisled transept at the east, galleries, and low clerestory windows. Each wing of the transept is separated into three parts by a Π-shaped colonnade. The cenotaph of saint Demetrios was placed in the chapel incorporated into the north-west end of the north aisles. To the southeast corner of the basilica was added a small three-aisled chapel dedicated to saint Euthymios. It was frescoed in 1303, at the behest of protostrator Michael Glavas Tarchaneiotis and his wife Maria Palaiologina. The program of the chapel is typical of the period, with scenes from the Dodekaorton, the miracles and teaching of Christ, and episodes from the life of saint Euthymios. Apart from the sculptural decoration of the capitals, the cornices, the impost blocks of the pilasters, the intrados of the tribelon and the wings in a variety of forms and styles, parts of the original marble revetment and the panels of opus sectile are still preserved on the walls. The basilica also contains the marble funerary monument of a wealthy merchant and notable of the city of Thessaloniki, Loukas Spantounis, buried there just after 1481. The mosaic decoration of the basilica was not destroyed completely by the fire of 1917. Fragments are still preserved on the two large piers at the east of the sanctuary and the west wall of the nave. The mosaic panels were not created as a part of an iconographic program, but were commissioned independently; some of them dating from before the 7th century fire, some date from the period of reconstruction that followed the fire, while the latest ones are 11th-century creations. They depict saint Demetrios orans with donors and in other cases they commemorate the saint's actions and miracles. The 9th-century mosaic panel depicts the Virgin and a military Saint in an attitude of supplication with Christ blessing from the heavens. Two more fragments of mosaics were detached and are currently displayed at the White Tower of Thessaloniki. The basilica was also decorated with frescoes destroyed during the fire of 1917. The ones that have survived depict scenes from the life of saint Demetrios. On the south wall survives a scene depicting a mounted emperor (identified as either Justinian II or Basil II) entering the city. On the second pier of the colonnade, south of the central aisle was represented in the 11th century venerable (Osios in Greek) Loukas Steiriotis, a 10th-century saint. On the first pier of the same colonnade was depicted between 1360-1380 saint Ioasaph with a church father. A Deisis (Christ flanked by Virgin Mary and Saint John the Baptist) and Christ enthroned painted in the 14th century were uncovered after the restoration of the monument, following the fire of 1917.

Date Range: 300 CE - 1917 CE

Region: Thessaloniki, Basilica of Saint Demetrios

Region tags: Greece, Thessaloniki

The basilica of saint Demetrios in Thessaloniki

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Cormack, R., "The Mosaic Decoration of S. Demetrios, Thessaloniki: A Re-examination in the Light of the Drawings of W. S. George", *The Annual of the British School at Athens*, 64 (1969), 17-52
- Source 2: Sotiriou, G. and Sotiriou, M., *Η Βασιλική του Αγίου Δημητρίου Θεσσαλονίκης*, Athens, 1952
- Source 3: Xyngoroulos, A., *Η βασιλική του Αγίου Δημητρίου Θεσσαλονίκης*, Thessaloniki, 1946

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.thebyzantinelegacy.com/demetrios-thessaloniki>
- Source 1 Description: Detailed description of the architecture and the decoration of saint Demetrios basilica
- Source 2 URL: <https://medievalmosaics.com/mosaics/65>
- Source 2 Description: The mosaics of saint Demetrios basilica

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1917-1948

Notes: The excavations started just after the fire of 1917. They ended just before the inauguration of the basilica in 1948.

- ↳ Name of excavation
 - Official or descriptive name: unknown

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Water source

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- Yes

- ↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
 - No

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
 - Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

- Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - Yes

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- ↳ The structure has a definite shape
 - Other [specify]: cross-transept basilica

- ↳ One single feature
 - Other [specify]: the basilica is a combination of a variety of features

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

- ↳ Worship:
 - Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes

- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– Other [specify]: it was destroyed by accident

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Other [specify]: it is not known

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: it was rebuilt after the fire of 1917

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: saint Demetrios

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– Yes

Notes: the basilica contains the cenotaph of saint Demetrios

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: In the 5th century it was built by the governor Leontios. In the 7th century it was rebuilt by the bishop of Thessaloniki and Leo the eparch

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: it was built following the transfer of the cult of saint Demetrios from Sirmium to Thessaloniki

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

- ↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:
 - Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

- Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

- No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

- No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

- No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

- Yes

- ↳ Earth
 - Yes

- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No

- ↳ Sand
 - Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: marble, glass, gold, and silver for the mosaics

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saint Demetrios, saint Loukas Steiriotis, saint Ioasaph, Deisis (Christ flanked by Virgin Mary and Saint John the Baptist) and Christ enthroned

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: doves, rams and eagles at the corner of the abacus, capitals with waving leaves, and fold capitals

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

Notes: The paintings are representing the deeds of saint Demetrius, an emperor entering a city and saints

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: an emperor entering a city

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: the paintings were largely destroyed by fire, so we do not have a clear picture of the iconographical programme of the frescoes

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: actions and miracles of saint Demetrios

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: donors depicted with saint Demetrios

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: they inform on the content or the scenes or the identity of the persons depicted

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: the funerary monument of Loukas Spandounis has also an inscription

- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - Yes
 - Notes: angels

- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No

- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No

- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - No

- ↳ Humans
 - Yes

- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - Yes
 - Notes: actions and miracles of saint Demetrios

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: actions and miracles of saint Demetrios

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: humans (patrons of the church, or their children) are also represented with saints

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: the basilica contains though the cenotaph of saint Demetrios. Soon after 1481 was buried therein Loukas Spantounis

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Loukas Spantounis was buried in the basilica

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: the basilica contains the cenotaph of saint Demetrios

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: the basilica was constructed on the occasion of the transfer of the cult of saint Demetrios to Thessaloniki and so the cenotaph of the saint exists in the monument

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: they pray to God

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: yes with saints and in particular with saint Demetrios

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: sometimes this happens as well with ex-votos

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: wine, olive oil and bread for the services

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: material offerings to a Christian Orthodox church can be anything from very precious objects to small everyday objects

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: it is required for the preservation of the monument

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: the monument is also maintained also by specialists working under the direction of the Ephorate of Byzantine antiquities of the city of Thessaloniki

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

Notes: services

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: such as baptisms, weddings, funerals

On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: impossible to specify

How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: every day

Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: the liturgy and the various services are synchronic practices

Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Yes

Notes: there are services in the basilica every day

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: male priests and monks

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Orthodox clergy is organised following an hierarchical system

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: the Metropolis of Thessaloniki

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: P. Lemerle. "Saint Démétrius de Thessalonique et les problèmes du martyrium et du transept. In: Bulletin de correspondance hellénique".

Reference: E. Tsigaridas. Οι τοιχογραφίες του παρεκκλησίου του Αγίου Ευθυμίου (1302/3) στον ναό του Αγίου Δημητρίου Έργο του Μανουήλ Πανσέληνου στην Θεσσαλονίκη. Thessaloniki:

Reference: R. Cormack. "Saint Demetrios of Thessaloniki: The powers of Art and Ritual, Themes of Unity and Diversity". (I. Lavin, Ed.), Acts of the XXVIth International Congress of History of Art (1986). London:

Reference: A. Grabar. "Quelques reliquaires de Saint Demetrios et le martyrium du saint à Salonique!".

Reference: I. Pallas. "Le ciborium hexagonal de Saint-Demetrios de Thessalonique".

Reference: I. Maitos. Ο ναός του Αγίου Δημητρίου. Thessaloniki:

Reference: Byzantine Legacy Church of St. Demetrios

Reference: Liz James Thessaloniki, St Demetrios

Reference: A. Χηγγοπουλος. Η βασιλική του Αγίου Δημητρίου Θεσσαλονίκης. Thessaloniki:

Reference: G. Sotiriou , M. Sotiriou. Η Βασιλική του Αγίου Δημητρίου Θεσσαλονίκης. Athens:

Reference: R. Cormack. "The Mosaic Decoration of S. Demetrios, Thessaloniki: A Re-examination in the Light of the Drawings of W. S. George".

Reference: A. Mentzos. "Η "ιστορική τοιχογραφία" του ναού του αγίου Δημητρίου". Μακεδονικά, 34(1)